

INTERVENTION CARRIED OUT IN THE LEFT SIDE DAM OF THE PIMENTAL SITE OF THE BELO MONTE HPP DURING THE FILLING OF THE RESERVOIR

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Abstract. *This work reports the intervention carried out in the stretch between Stakes 205 and 235 in the Left Side Dam of the Pimental Site of the Belo Monte HPP. This intervention was due to excessive increases of the uplift pressure in the foundation of the dam of this stretch, above those foreseen in the project, during and after the filling of the reservoir. The reinforcement solutions adopted still during the rise of the reservoir level are presented, in order to ensure the safety factors regarding the stability of the structure, both in emergency and permanent terms, as recommended in the design criteria.*

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Left Side Dam (LSD) of the Pimental Site extends from the left wall of the Assembly Area, located on Marciana Island, to the left bank, for an extension of approximately 5,080m. The geological anomaly, one of the objects of this presentation, is located in a 600m stretch between the stakes 205 and 235.

The Figure 1, shows the location of the LSD in the arrangement of the structures of the Pimental Site, with indication of the stretch, object of the interventions.

Figure 1 – General arrangement of the Pimental Site

In this region, the dam has an average height of approximately 14m and the typical cross-section (presented in figure 3) is a homogeneous earthfill dam, with a crest width of 7.0m and a downstream slope of 1V: 1,8H from its base to El. 95.00m followed by 1V: 1.6H until El. 100.00m. The upstream slope is 1V: 2H from its base up to El. 93.50m followed by 1V: 1,8H slope up to El. 97,50m and ending with 1V: 1,6H up to El. 100,00m. It also presents Rip-Rap from the elevation 93.50m with $D_{50} = 0.6\text{m}$. The downstream slope protection from the foundation up to the 95.40 m elevation is Rip-Rap and plant protection at the top.

The foundation, described in more detail in item 3, consists of an alluvial layer of silty clay at the upper level of the terrain, followed by a sandy alluvial layer, overlaid the tremolite residual soil, which transition below into the tremolite rock.

The drainage system consists of a 0.70m wide vertical sand filter and horizontal drainage layers with sand and gravel above foundation. In central part of section those are interconnected by the suspended horizontal sand filter in El. 88,50m followed by the vertical sand filter. It is also provided with a drainage trench at the toe of the dam.

It should be emphasized that it was foreseen in the executive project that this downstream drainage trench, consisting of sand, would completely cross the clayey alluvium layer, penetrating 0.50m in the layer of the underlying alluvial sandy layer, as shown in Figure 2, which would ensure dissipation of higher pore pressure in the downstream region of the dam.

Figura 2 – Detail of the drainage trench executive project from the stretch between stakes 205 and 235, where the sand trench (3-C) penetrates 0,50m in the sandy alluvium.

The cut-off consists of a compacted backfill trench intercepting the alluvium, with the base supported, in this particular stretch, predominantly in residual soil of tremolitite, being in the other stretches supported on the top of the migmatite rock. This cut-off is located on the outside, upstream of the dam body, because the project previously predicted jet grouting curtain sealing, which was carried out after the landfill rise. With the investigation of the upstream region, already with the execution of the landfill in progress, it was verified that the bedrock was higher than the central region, fact that motivated the change of the project to cut off-of compacted soil.

2 HIGH UPLIFT PRESSURE IN THE FOUNDATION, DETECTED THROUGH INSTRUMENTATION READINGS

The filling began on November, 24th of 2015 and between the 16th and 23rd of December, when the level of the reservoir was around the El. 92.80m, readings were observed above those foreseen in several piezometers installed in the downstream of the stretch between stakes 205 and 235.

In addition, no water seepage was observed through the toe drain in this stretch, as expected, indicating that the drain trench was inoperative.

In view of this behavior, the decision was made to immediately start the execution of equilibrium berms, consisting of rockfill with fines, aiming at the recovery of the safety factor (SF) regarding the foundation uplifting in this downstream region, considering the probable worsening of the situation with the imminent rise of the reservoir up to El. 97,00m. Figures 3 and 4 show the dimensioning section and the plant with the equilibrium berm.

The rise of this berm was carried out in stages, in order to preserve a provisional minimum safety factor of 1.20 in relation to the uplifting of the foundation, assuming projections of uplifts according to the water level of the reservoir, concluding with the configuration presented in figures 3 and 4. This final configuration guarantees a minimum safety factor of 1.50 for both global stability and localized foundation uplifting in the downstream region.

Simultaneously to the execution of this berm, 21 additional piezometers were installed in this downstream region for monitoring the uplifts, as well as the execution of a line of relief wells downstream of the reinforcement berm, with spacings of 6.00 m, 3.00 m and even 1,50m.

In Figures 5 and 6, the photos show the construction of the equilibrium berm and the relief wells and in Figure 7 the photo shows the current situation (October, 26th of 2016), remaining to construct the drainage channel for collection of the water from the relief wells to complete the planned intervention.

Figure 3: Typical cross section with the piezometry projected for NA m = 97.00m and berms dimensioned with FS = 1,50 for failure by lifting of the foundation.

Figure 4: Dam plan in the stretch between the stakes 205 and 235 with berms in the following elevations: dark gray color = 91.00 m; brown color = 90.00 m; blue color = 89.00 m and lilac = 88.20 m.

Figure 5: View of the left bank to the right during construction of the equilibrium berm

Figure 6: View of flowing relief wells, in the downstream region of the equilibrium berm

Figure 7: View, from downstream to left bank, of the current situation of the equilibrium berm in the stretch between the stakes 205 and 235

3 GEOLOGICAL-GEOTECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FOUNDATION IN THE STRETCH BETWEEN THE STAKES 205 AND 235

The BLE foundation of the Pimental Site in the stretch in question, as shown in the longitudinal geological-geotechnical section presented in Figure 8, is characterized by an alluvial deposit with a variable thickness between 4.5m and 8m (mean of 6m), based predominantly on young residual soil and, locally, on the migmatite bedrock. In the stretch between the approximate stakes 215 and 235, the migmatite is characterized by the predominance of lithology of tonalitic composition, of fine texture, dark gray, rich in amphibole - tremolite, reason why it was denominated of tremolitite.

This lithology represents, apparently, a subvertical body, of basic origin, positioned transversely to the axis of the dam, relatively well preserved in the process of migmatization (granitization) to which the rocks of the Xingu Complex (stratigraphic denomination of the group of lithologies of the crystalline basement that appear in the region) were submitted in the Proterozoic.

The alluvium is generally characterized by an upper layer consisting of silty clay with a thickness of 2m to 6m (mean of 4m), overlaid on medium to coarse sand banks with variations for fine to medium and fine with or without clay, consisting of rounded quartz grains, often having a decimetric / sub-metric level with a concentration of pebbles up to 2 cm in diameter at the base.

The silty clay presents a permeability coefficient ranging from 1×10^{-5} cm/s to 5×10^{-4} cm/s, and may be more permeable in places with a higher concentration of canaliculi, which are frequent in this soil, with probably due to rotten roots associated with microfauna (e.g., termites).

The sands have very variable permeabilities, between 5×10^{-5} cm/s and 4×10^{-3} cm/s, the lowest values in the little clayey fine sand levels / lenses and the higher permeabilities in medium to coarse sand and coarse sand with pebbles banks.

The young residual soil from tremolitite presents a variable thickness between 5m and 12m (mean of 7m) at the cut off axis, being absent at the range of cuttings 230 to 235 (both in the cut off axis and downstream of the dam), and locally on the 221 + 15m (cut off line).

As verified in the soundings, the residual soil occurs interspersed with moderately to highly weathered and fractured rock, it is micaceous and its grain size distribution is very varied, between silty fine sand and clay-sandy silt or even sandy clay, from black to dark gray, greenish or variegated colors. Its permeability in the soundings boreholes performed on the cut off axis varies between 1.4×10^{-4} cm / s and 2.3×10^{-3} cm/ s, being locally (SM-5011) very permeable throughout almost all the soil profile, which reaches 10m thick .

The rock mass, where outcropping, and even the depth reached in the mixed surveys performed in the cut off axis (5 to 10m in rock), is generally moderately weathered (A2), medium to very fractured (F3 to F4) and with conductivity hydraulics of the order of 10^{-3} cm/s, locally more sealed, between 10^{-4} cm/s and 10^{-5} cm/s.

Deeper soundings executed on the axis of the dam near the edge of the tremolitite body (SR-5008, SR-5008A, SR-5008B and SR-5009A) show sound rock mass, slightly fractured and impermeable below 5m depth.

Legend: red color - residual soil of migmatite (characterized by the tremolite lithology between the approximate cuttings 215 and 235); yellow and orange color - sandy alluvium; green color – silty-clay alluvium; pink color – fill.

Figure 8: Geological-geotechnical longitudinal section of the stretch between stakes 205 and 235

The longitudinal section of Figure 8 was made using the data from the rotary and mixed drillings performed on the dam and cut off axis and the data obtained from the rotary and rotopercussive drillings performed in the alignment where the additional piezometers PZT's 01 a 19 were installed (at 55m and 76m downstream of the dam axis).

From the drillings performed in the dam and cut off axis, it was obtained the bedrock line and the soil and mass rock permeability results (from infiltration and water loss tests). The rotopercussive drillings were used to trace the lower limit of the alluvial deposit and the limits between its layers of different grains size. The rotary drilling, performed in the 55m alignment downstream of the axis, allowed local adjustments to the bedrock line and also localized checking of the alluvial layers grain size description, which had been made through the tactile-visual analysis of washed samples of the rotopercussive drillings.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The high uplift in the downstream region of the stretch in question was probably due mainly to the non-functioning of the downstream drainage trench. The relatively high permeability of the "tremolite" residual soil, with values very close to the overlying alluvial sand, not detected at the time of project design, resulted in the low efficiency of the cut-off system, with head losses lower than expected, a fact that also contributed to the increase of uplifts in the downstream region, by concentrating a good part of the head losses in the upper layer of clayey alluvium, and without the expected relief of the drainage trench.

In a simplified simulation study of percolation, as shown in Figure 9, considering the non-operant drainage trench and approximate pore pressures obtained in the readings of the instruments, the situation is observed with greater clarity. This study further shows that to obtain the result, the permeability contrast between the upper silty clay and the underlying sandy alluvium / residual soil of tremolite would have to be approximately 100 times.

Figure 9: Equipotentials obtained in the percolation study simulating the condition of piezometries corresponding to reservoir water level of upstream of 96.50m.

It is also verified in the studies, as shown in Figure 10, that the output hydraulic gradient is relatively high in the downstream direction, reaching values of 0.70, which conditioned the execution of the relief wells to avoid possible located points with regressive erosion ("piping") in the foundation, at downstream of the equilibrium berm.

Figure 10: Curves of equal hydraulic gradients (XY) in the downstream region, obtained in the seepage study presented in Figure 9.

At the time of detection of the elevated readings of the piezometers of the stretch, the execution of the wells or even the relief drain adjacent to the toe drain was considered, however, due to the fear of instability of the alluvium sand due to the high uplift, as well as to the imminent rise in the level of the reservoir up to the El. 97.00m, it was decided

for the immediate execution of the equilibrium berm, with increase in stages as already mentioned.

As shown in Figure 11, the piezometric levels verified in the instruments of section 222 + 10, two months after the filling of the reservoir, were all below the levels of attention, fact also verified in all the other instruments of the mentioned stretch, attesting the correctness of the measures adopted, which ensured for this 600m stretch of the dam a safety factor according to the design criteria.

Legend: N.At. - Attention Level; N.Al. - Alert Level; C.P. - Piezometric Level

Figure 11: Piezometric readings of March, 28th, 2016 of the instruments of E. 222 + 10

In order to reach at the above configuration (figure 9) that approximates the readings obtained in the piezometers the following permeabilities of the materials were admitted: Tremolite rock mass - 5×10^{-4} cm/s; Tremolite residual soil - 5×10^{-3} cm/s; Sandy alluvial soil - 5×10^{-3} cm/s; Silty-clay alluvial soil - 5×10^{-5} cm/s; Compacted earthfill - $K_h - 4 \times 10^{-6}$ cm/s and $K_v - 10^{-6}$ cm/s.

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6 BIBLIOGRAPHY

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